

Isocoumrins. Part II. Preparation and Cyclisation of some 2-Carboxyphenylacetaldehydes

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5-Methoxy-, 5,6-dimethoxy-, and 4,5-methylenedioxy-2-carboxyphenylacetaldehydes have been prepared and cyclised with phosphoric acid to 6-methoxy-, 5,6-dimethoxy-, and 6,7-methylenedioxy-isocoumarins, respectively.

A convenient route for the synthesis of 6,7-dimethoxyisocoumarin involving the periodate oxidation of 2-hydroxy-5,6-dimethoxyindan-1-one, prepared from its 2-diazo analogue and cyclisation of the resulting 2-carboxy-4,5-dimethoxyphenylacetaldehyde, has already been reported¹. Since the yields were good at each stage, the present workers have been exploring this method as a general synthetic route to isocoumarins. Based on the same reaction sequences, 6-methoxy-, 5,6-dimethoxy-, and 6,7-methylenedioxy-isocoumarins have been synthesised and this route proves better than those reported earlier²⁻³ for preparing the isocoumarins.

(I)

(II)

(III)

(IV)

a: R=5-OMe.

a: R=5-OMe;

R₁=H.

a: R=5-OMe.

a: R=6-OMe.

b: R=4,5-di-OMe.

b: R=4,5-di-OMe; R₁=H.

b: R=5,6-di-OMe.

b: R=5,6-di-OMe.

c: R=5,6-O₂CH₂.

c: R=5,6-O₂CH₂;

R₁=H.

c: R=4, 5-O₂CH₂.

c: R=6,7-O₂CH₂.

d: R=5-OMe;

R₁=OAc.

e: R=4,5-di-OMe;

R₁=OAc.

f: R=5,6-O₂CH₂;

R₁=OAc.

g: R=5-OMe;

R₁=OH.

h: R=4,5-di-OMe;

R₁=OH.

i: R=5,6-O₂CH₂;

R₁=OH.

Thus the 2-oximino derivatives⁴⁻⁵ of the indan-1-ones (II,a-c), on treatment with sodium hypochlorite in presence of ammonium hydroxide, furnished the 2-diazoindan-1-

1. Bose and Chaudhury, *this Journal*, 1965, 42, 211.

2. Srivastava and Chaudhury, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1962, 27, 4397.

3. Mukhopadhyay and Chaudhury, *this Journal*, 1963, 40, 439.

4. Chakravarti and Srinathan, *ibid.*, 1934, 11, 101.

5. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1907, 1084.

ones (I,a-c) which with glacial acetic acid yielded the acetates (II,d-f). Deacetylation with potassium carbonate at 0° provided the 2-hydroxyindan-1-ones (II, g-i) and subsequent oxidation with periodic acid afforded the *ortho*-carboxyphenylacetaldehydes (III, a-c). The aqueous ethanolic solution of 2-hydroxy-5-methoxyindan-1-one (II,g) was smoothly oxidised, but the oxidation of the other two hydroxyindan-1-ones (II,h and i) by this procedure was not successful as these were almost insoluble in aqueous ethanol at 0°. This difficulty was obviated by the inverse addition of a solution of (II,h) in methyl cellosolve and of (II,i) in dioxane to aqueous periodic acid at 0°.

Finally, the 2-carboxyaldehydes (III, a-c) were smoothly cyclised with orthophosphoric acid to the corresponding isocoumarins (IV, a-c)²⁻³.

*EXPERIMENTAL

5-Methoxy-2-oximinoindan-1-one was obtained by the following modification of the literature method⁴. Isoamyl nitrite (2.5 ml) was added to a stirred solution of (II, a; 6g.) in methyl cellosolve (80 ml) and HCl (10 ml, conc.) when a solid began to separate within 6 min. Isoamyl nitrite (2.5 ml) was again added and the mixture was stirred for 1/2 hr. It was then poured on cold water; the product was filtered and washed well with water and dilute ethanol. Crystallisation from glacial acetic acid furnished the pure oximino compound as pale yellow needles (6.4 g., 96.9%), m.p. 220° (decomp.); lit.⁴ m.p. 221° (decomp.)

2-Diazo-5-methoxyindan-1-one (I,a).—A solution of the preceding compound (3 g.) in NaOH (0.32*N*, 50 ml) was stirred and cooled to -3°, when after 2 min. a portion of the sodium salt separated. 15*N*-NH₄OH (2 ml) was then added, followed by dropwise addition of NaOCl solution (5.36%, 50 ml) during 45 min., the temperature being maintained throughout at -3°. The reaction mixture was held at this temperature for 1/2 hr. after the addition was complete. The ice bath was then removed and stirring continued, when the diazo compound separated at 1°. The reaction mixture on stirring for further 2 hr. gradually attained the room temperature (32°). The diazo compound was filtered, washed with water, and dried in an exiccator. It weighed 2.7 g. (91.8%), m.p. 102-103° (decomp.), and was used for the next step without further purification. A sample, crystallised from ethyl acetate, furnished a specimen of pure (I,a) in pale yellow needles, m.p. 103-104° (decomp.). (Found: C, 63.4; H, 4.5; N, 14.1. C₁₀H₈O₂N₂ requires C, 63.8; H, 4.2; N, 14.3%).

2-Acetoxy-5-methoxyindan-1-one (II,d).—To the diazoketone (I,a; 4 g.) glacial acetic acid (25 ml) was added gradually when N₂ evolved copiously and a clear solution was obtained. After 1/2 hr. it was diluted with water (120 ml) and extracted with ethyl acetate. The extract was washed with aqueous sodium bicarbonate and water and dried. Evaporation of the solvent left a gummy residue which gradually solidified to a yellow crystalline paste. Chromatography of the crude product in benzene through a column of Brockmann alumina, followed by crystallisation from methanol, yielded pure (II,d) as colorless needles (3.5 g., 79.5%), m.p. 78-79°. (Found: C, 65.1; H, 5.7. C₁₂H₁₂O₄ requires C, 65.4; H, 5.4%). It reduced hot Fehling's solution.

* All m.p.s are uncorrected. Light petroleum used had b.p. 60-80°. Na₂SO₄ was used for drying all extracts with organic solvents. The method of Shine (*J. Org. Chem.*, 1959, 24, 252) was adopted for the preparation of all 2,4-DNPs.

Its 2,4-*DNP* was obtained as orange needles from dioxane, m.p. 230° (decomp.). (Found: N, 13.8. $C_{18}H_{16}O_2N_4$ requires N, 13.7%).

2-Hydroxy-5-methoxyindan-1-one (II, g).—To a solution of (II, d; 1g.) in methyl callosolve (25 ml) at 0° was added K_2CO_3 (0.7 g. in 10 ml water) and kept in a refrigerator overnight. It was diluted with cold water (80 ml), thoroughly extracted with $CHCl_3$, and the extract washed with dilute HCl and water. Evaporation of the dried extract left the ketol as almost colorless, irregular prisms (0.75 g., 93.7%), m.p. 131-32°. A sample crystallised from ethyl acetate-light petroleum furnished the colorless analytical specimen, m.p. 133-34°. (Found: C, 67.2; H, 5.8. $C_{16}H_{10}O_3$ requires C, 67.4; H, 5.6%). It readily reduced Fehling's solution in cold and formed a blue precipitate with baryta, a characteristic test⁶ for cyclic ketols.

Its 2,4-*DNP* formed red needles (from dioxane), m.p. 226° (decomp.). (Found: N, 15.8. $C_{16}H_{14}O_6N_4$ requires N, 15.6%).

2-Carboxy-5-methoxyphenylacetaldehyde (III, a).—An ice-cold solution of HIO_4 (1.07 g. in 12.2 ml water) was added to a stirred solution of (II, g; 1g.) in water (15 ml) and ethanol (10 ml) at 0°, when after 4 min. a crystalline material started separating. The reaction mixture was kept at 0° for 10 min. and then at the room temperature for 1/2 hr. The crystals were collected, washed with ice-cold water, and recrystallised from ethyl acetate to furnish pure (III, a) as colorless needles (1.05 g., 97.2%), m.p. 152-53°. (Found: C, 62.0; H, 5.4. $C_{10}H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 61.8; H, 5.1%).

6-Methoxyisocoumarin (IV, a).—A mixture of (III, a; 1g.) and H_3PO_4 (d 1.75, 4 ml) was heated at 120° for 15 min. and the resulting brown liquid was poured on ice. The precipitate separating was filtered, washed with aqueous sodium bicarbonate and water, and dried in an exiccator. It was dissolved in benzene and chromatographed through a column of Brockmann's alumina, using the same solvent as eluent. The benzene was distilled and the residue was crystallised from ethyl acetate-light petroleum to furnish the pure isocoumarin (IV, a) as colorless needles (0.9 g., 99%), m.p. 96-97°, undepressed on admixture with an authentic specimen, m.p. 98°, prepared earlier⁸ by a different route.

2-Diazo-4,5-dimethoxyindan-1-one (I, b) was prepared according to the procedure described for (Ia). Thus a solution of 4,5-dimethoxy-2-oximinoindan-1-one⁴ (1.71 g.) in NaOH (0.32*N*, 25 ml), 15*N*- NH_4OH (1 ml), and NaOCl solution (5.25%, 25 ml) were employed. The sodium salt of the oximino compound separated at 0°, whereas the diazoketone, at 5°. Crystallisation from ethyl acetate provided (I, b) as yellow needles (1.5 g., 89.8%), m.p. 136-37° (decomp.). (Found: C, 66.7; H 4.2; N 13.0. $C_{11}H_{10}O_5N_2$ requires C, 66.5; H, 4.5; N, 12.8%).

2-Acetoxy-4,5-dimethoxyindan-1-one (II, e) was prepared by the interaction of (II, b; 2 g.) and glacial acetic acid (20 ml) as in the case of (II, d). The pale yellow solid separating after pouring the reaction solution on ice was purified by chromatography in benzene over Brockmann's alumina, followed by crystallisation from water. Pure (II, e) was isolated in needles (2g., 90.9%), m.p. 87-88°. (Found: C, 62.1; H, 5.3. $C_{13}H_{14}O_6$ requires C, 62.4; H, 5.6%).

Its 2,4-*DNP* was obtained as scarlet needles (from diglyme), m.p. 232-33° (decomp.). (Found: N, 13.30. $C_{19}H_{18}O_8N_4$ requires N, 13.02%).

6. *Annalen*, Criegee and Klönk, 1949, 564, 1.

2-Hydroxy-4,5-dimethoxyindan-1-one (II,h).—A solution of K_2CO_3 (1.4 g.) in water (20 ml) was added to a stirred solution of the preceding compound (2 g.) in methanol (40 ml) at 0° and the reaction mixture kept in a refrigerator overnight. The crystalline mass separating was collected, well washed with water, and dried in an exiccator. Crystallisation from ethanol yielded pure (II,h) in colorless needles (1.56 g., 93.0%), m.p. 178-79°. (Found: C, 63.2; H, 5.9. $C_{11}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 63.4; H, 5.7%). It reduced Fehling's solution in the cold and with baryta⁵ formed a blue precipitate.

Its 2,4-DNP was obtained as red needles (from dioxane), m.p. 236-37° (decomp.). (Found: N, 14.2. $C_{17}H_{16}O_7N_4$ requires N, 14.4%).

2-Carboxy-5,6-dimethoxyphenylacetaldehyde (III,b).—A cooled solution of (II,b; 1 g.) in methyl cellosolve (40 ml) was added dropwise to a stirred solution of HIO_4 (0.92 g. in 10.5 ml water) at 0° and the mixture kept in a refrigerator overnight. It was diluted with water (200 ml) and extracted thoroughly with ethyl acetate (3×15 ml). The combined extract was repeatedly washed with aqueous sodium carbonate; the alkaline washings were combined, cooled, and acidified with HCl (dil.), when colorless needles (1 g., 93.4%), m.p. 186-87°, separated. A sample crystallised from ethyl acetate afforded the analytical specimen of (III,b), m.p. 186-87°. (Found: C, 59.2; H, 5.6. $C_{11}H_{12}O_6$ requires C, 59.9; H, 5.3%).

5,6-Dimethoxyisocoumarin (IVb).—Cyclisation of (III,b, 0.8 g.) was effected with H_3PO_4 (d 1.75, 2.5 ml) at 130-40° for 40 min. as in the case of (IV,a). The almost colorless residue, left after evaporation of the benzene, was recrystallised from ethyl acetate-light petroleum to yield the pure isocoumarin (IV,b) in long fine needles (0.71 g., 99.4%), m.p. 90°, undepressed on admixture with an authentic specimen, m.p. 90°, prepared earlier² by a different route.

5,6-Methylenedioxy-2-oximinoindan-1-one.—The literature method⁵ was modified to obtain a better yield. Isoamyl nitrite (5 ml) was added to a solution of (II,c; 13 g.) in methyl cellosolve (60 ml) and HCl (conc., 5 ml). The solid began to separate within 4 min. and an additional quantity of isoamyl nitrite (5 ml) was added. It was worked up according to the procedure described above for the preparation of 5-methoxy-2-oximinoindan-1-one. Recrystallisation from glacial acetic acid afforded the pure oximino compound in yellow needles (13.2 g., 92.3%), m.p. 229° (decomp.); lit.⁵ m.p. 229-30° (decomp.).

2-Diazo-5,6-methylenedioxyindan-1-one (I,c) was prepared according to the procedure described for (II,a). A solution of the preceding compound (3 g.) in NaOH (0.32*N*, 50 ml), 15 *N*- NH_4OH (2 ml) and NaOCl solution (5.36%, 50 ml) were employed. The sodium salt separated at -1°, but the diazo compound at 1°. Purification by crystallisation from ethyl acetate afforded (I,c) in pale yellow needles (2.7 g., 91.8%), m.p. 163-64° (decomp.). (Found: C, 59.8; H, 3.1; N, 13.2. $C_{10}H_{10}O_3N_2$ requires C, 59.4; H, 2.9; N, 13.3%).

2-Acetoxy-5,6-methylenedioxyindan-1-one (II,f) was prepared by the interaction of (I,c; 3 g.) and glacial acetic acid (20 ml) as in (II,e). The almost pure product isolated after chromatography in benzene was crystallised from water to afford (II,f) in colorless needles (2.7 g., 81.8%), m.p. 126-27°. (Found: C, 61.3; H, 4.1. $C_{12}H_{10}O_5$ requires C, 61.5; H, 4.2%).

Its 2,4-DNP was crystallised from dioxane in crimson needles, m.p. 246-47° (decomp.). (Found: N, 11.3. $C_{18}H_{14}O_8N_4$ requires N, 11.1%).

2-Hydroxy-5,8-methylenedioxyindan-1-one (II,i).—Deacetylation of the preceding compound (3 g.) in methyl cellosolve (50 ml) was effected with K_2CO_3 (2.1 g. in 30 ml water) as in the case of (II,g). Recrystallisation from water furnished pure (II,i) in colorless needles (2.1 g., 85.3%), m.p. 154-55°. (Found: C, 62.6; H, 4.4. $C_{10}H_8O_4$ requires C, 62.6; H, 4.1%). It reduced Fehling's solution in the cold and formed a blue precipitate with baryta⁶.

Its 2,4-DNP formed maroon needles (from diglyme), m.p. 238-30° (decomp.). (Found: N, 15.2. $C_{16}H_{12}O_7N_4$ requires N, 15.05%).

2-Carboxy-4,5-methylenedioxyphenylacetaldehyde (III,c).—A solution of (II,i) in dioxane (8 ml) was added dropwise with stirring to a solution of HIO_4 (0.5 g. in 5.7 ml water) at 0° and worked up as in (III,a). Recrystallisation from ethyl acetate afforded pure (III,c) in colorless needles (0.45 g., 83.3%), m.p. 166-57°. (Found: C, 57.9; H, 4.1. $C_{10}H_6O_5$ requires C, 57.6; H, 3.8%).

6,7-Methylenedioxyisocoumarin (IV,c).—A mixture of (III,c; 0.2 g.) and H_3PO_4 (d 1.75, 1 ml) was heated at 115-20° for 7 min. and worked up as in the case of (IV,a). The residue left after evaporation of the benzene was crystallised successively from ethyl acetate and methanol to furnish pure (IV,c) as colorless, rectangular prisms (0.18 g., 99.9%), m.p. 169-70°, undepressed on admixture with an authentic specimen, m.p. 168-69°, prepared earlier⁸ by a different route.

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Received November 30, 1965.